

PHILOSOPHY OF POLITICAL PERSUASION**Shernazarov Ravshan Avazovich**

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Annotation: This article examines the concept of political persuasion, exploring how it articulates an individual's political views, thoughts, and decisions. It highlights the pivotal role of this concept in shaping political processes and contributing to the advancement of state and society. Additionally, it facilitates the analysis of human experiences, social issues, and perspectives.

Key words: development, philosophy, democracy, society, morality, equality, justice, freedom, upbringing, knowledge.

Political persuasion encompasses an individual's deeply held beliefs, attitudes, and values concerning political processes, institutions, ideologies, and governance. These convictions influence how people perceive and interpret political developments, policies, and leaders. Various factors shape political persuasions, including personal experiences, upbringing, education, socio-economic status, cultural background, and exposure to diverse sources of information.

These persuasions span a spectrum from broad ideologies such as liberalism, conservatism, socialism, or nationalism, to specific stances on issues like healthcare, immigration, environmental policies, or foreign relations. They frequently guide individuals' political actions, including voting choices, engagement in political movements, and fulfilling civic responsibilities.

It is known that there are emotional and mental foundations to a worldview. The emotional basis forms a person's ideas about the world, while the intellectual basis shapes their direct views of the world [1]. Therefore, the process of forming political persuasions, which is foundational to one's worldview, begins with two pillars of support. One of these foundations is rooted in political emotions, experiences, and imagination, while the other is based on political information and knowledge. In other words, an individual's personal political persuasions are shaped by both their political emotions and their knowledge.

The initial support mechanism driving the formation of political persuasion is rooted in political emotions. Political persuasions emerge as emotional reflections of societal political existence. These feelings are shaped by external

political realities and manifest within human consciousness. They elicit emotional responses from individuals towards various political events and processes. These emotional attitudes manifest as political experiences, crucial structural elements of an individual's psyche. Thus, political experiences reflect a person's emotional reactions to political developments.

When political knowledge, understood in essence and confirmed in truth, aligns with the needs and interests of the individual, a desire to apply it in action arises. This knowledge then becomes a political standard that guides all of a person's political activities, subjecting them to specific rules and principles. A person becomes accustomed to engaging in any political activity within society based solely on these political standards, without deviation under any circumstance. Thus, the foundation of a person's political persuasions lies solely in political knowledge influenced by various political feelings and experiences, alongside political information that has successfully met the criteria of "understanding-believing-practicing".

Building on the aforementioned considerations, let's detail the definition and structure of the concept of "political persuasions". Political persuasions comprise political knowledge synthesized from emotions (political feelings and experiences) and intellect (political news and information), thoroughly understood, believed to be truthful, and put into practice. "An essential aspect of political persuasion is its reflection of an individual's stance on political authority and the internal and external policies of the state. Furthermore, political persuasion forms the cornerstone of a person's political culture" [2].

The composition of political persuasions can be envisioned as consisting of the following components:

➤ **Cognitive component:** This includes political information and knowledge, which encompass understanding political realities, information about political processes, concepts, judgments, and conclusions reflecting the social existence of society. This forms the epistemological basis of an individual's political persuasions.

➤ **Evaluation component:** This involves a person's attitudes towards political processes in society, shaped by their political experiences and knowledge. It establishes the axiological basis of a person's political persuasions, influencing their assessment of various political events and processes.

➤ **Activity component:** This pertains to a person's inclination to engage in political activities, driven by their political experiences and knowledge. It forms the praxeological basis of an individual's political

persuasions, reflecting their intentions and desires to alter existing political realities in alignment with their own values, ideals, and aspirations.

Of course, the depiction of the structure of political persuasions in the above manner is entirely hypothetical. In reality, political knowledge, values, and ideas do not exist separately in a person's worldview; rather, they intertwine and complement each other. Therefore, any structural representation is merely a model crafted to delve deeper into the essence of political persuasion.

The formation of political persuasion is crucial not only for individuals but also for society, as it serves several social functions in addition to personal ones. Specifically:

Firstly, political persuasion enhances the ability to mobilize members of society towards specific political goals. As more individuals develop their own political beliefs, the potential for implementing political programs increases.

Secondly, political persuasion acts as a catalyst for raising civic consciousness among members of society. Strengthened political beliefs foster a sense of citizenship, expanding people's perspectives on social development goals.

Thirdly, political persuasion fosters social solidarity. Shared political beliefs provide a common ground for agreement among people, which is essential for uniting individuals who might otherwise lack political ideas.

Fourthly, political persuasion helps stabilize social relations. Individuals with political beliefs understand and respect others who hold differing beliefs, fostering healthy social interactions within a developed democratic society.

Lastly, political persuasion serves as a safeguard for ideological security within society. An increase in the number of individuals with strong political beliefs limits the influence of foreign ideologies.

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